

The Impact of Slow and Circular Fashion Concept on Consumers Purchase Intention

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ABSTRACT: Slow and circular fashion concept is a concept that used in fashion industry referring to company or brand that produced clothes in sustainable practices, including reducing waste, extending lifespan of products, and priority responsible manufacture. As the textile manufacture is one of the biggest industry that producing waste, many people start to aware of this problem, especially millennials and gen Z. Many fashion brand are starting to apply sustainability process on their manufacture, including applying slow and circular fashion concept. As a sustainability brand, they tend to use value-based pricing on their pricing strategy, so the price range is middle to high. The brand wanted the value they offer to the consumers is delivered well and they tried to encourage people to be responsible consumers. However, the one who have awareness of environment concern are millennials and gen Z who have middle to low purchasing power. This generation sees the value that sustainability brand's offer is not appeal to them even though they know the brand mission and vision. This study aimed to identify factors that influence the consumers purchase intention on slow and circular fashion concept. This study using quantitative methods and descriptive statistic as data collection methods. The data were obtained from questionnaire that were distributed to 200 respondent.

KEYWORDS: descriptive statistic, marketing strategy, purchase intention, sustainable fashion brand, slow and circular fashion concept.

INTRODUCTION

The fashion industry considering doing fast fashion to improve their profit significantly. Fast fashion is called on the manufacture that producing on rapidly high volumes of clothes and producing leverages trend replication, almost every brand we see on department store is producing massive clothes. As fast fashion requires a lot of production, labor exploitation, industry waste, and many pollutions occur in those industry. According to United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), fashion industry has a huge impact on environment. Fashion industry responsible for 20% of global wastewater, 10% of carbon emissions and massive amounts of waste. BBC also stated that the average of people throws away their clothes is estimated around 92 million tonnes of textile waste that ends up on landfill sites. Every clothes that have been made up release around 1.2 billion tonnes of greenhouse gases into atmosphere every year. This situation tell that we should limit the consumption of clothes and start searching for brand that implying slow and circular fashion concept. People these days are concern and aware about their surrounding environment. For example, people willing to pay more on Eco-friendly product to show their concern on environment. The younger generation has increased awareness and concern for the environment, thus converts into a desire to invest in green products. Through their emphasis on sustainability and responsible production, Eco-friendly fashion clothes may appeal to them. Slow fashion concept refers to producing clothes that considering environmental, humane, social, and cultural aspects towards quality, also the clothes produced through more considered toward environment. (Murwanti, 2017). Circular fashion concept is a concept of loops inside fashion system by prioritizing clothes to be reuse, recycling, and upcycling (Aus et al., 2021). These concepts underline the significance of responsible consumption, durability, and resource efficiency. Consumers can help reduce the negative impact of fashion industry by purchasing slow and circular fashion products. Consumers can show their concern about environment by supporting businesses and project that promote responsible manufacturing, ethical labour methods, and conserving natural resources.

The increased consumer awareness of green products has a major impact for businesses and manufacturers. Companies have grown to recognize the importance of implementing sustainability into their basic strategies to comply with current consumer needs (Alamsyah, 2020). As a result, many businesses are adopting sustainable practices into their supply chains, creating green product lines, and taking steps to improve their general social responsibility. Businesses that align with consumer demands for green products not only help to preserve the environment, but they also gain a competitive advantage in a market that is becoming more influenced

by environmental concerns. The slow and circular fashion concept is one of the aspects for the green circular product and manufacturer by the fashion industry, knowing the effect they have on consumers' purchase intention will grow more important for the company marketing strategy. This research will conduct research of the effect of slow and circular fashion concept on consumers purchase intention, by identify several variables that might influence consumers on their purchase on slow and circular fashion product.

BUSINESS ISSUE

The younger generation (Millennials and Gen Z) are the generation that have higher awareness of environment concern while they want to participate in ecological act, they purchasing power is lower than the older generation. Eco-friendly products have higher value, than the ordinal product, and to buy those products the purchasing power must be high otherwise they can't buy it. Also, some people who aware of the environment concern but think that the product to expensive and not appeal to them because they not yet see the value of the product. Looking at this problem, this research wanted to search what kind of factor that can influence consumer purchase intention.

METHODOLOGY

This research used applied research approach, applied research is research conducted in the real world to answer specific problem of individuals, organizations, and/or industries (Baimyrzaeva, 2018). This research identifies customer analysis to know the behaviour of the consumers. Market-focused companies prioritize consumer satisfaction. The planning and execution of a company's marketing strategy begins with its consumers, or with the identification of their target market. Companies must understand how and why the targeting consumers purchase the products. This means that the business must have a thorough understanding of their potential market's consumer's purchasing habits and decision-making processes (Cuellar et al. 2013). The data for consumer analysis will be collected through primary data from questionnaire. The questionnaire will be proceeded in validity and reliability test. The answer from the respondent will be collected and processed with regression analysis.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Validity Test

The relevant and suitable interpretation of the data produced from the measuring instrument because of the analysis determines validity (Sürücü & Maslakçi, 2020). The question is valid if the R value bigger than the R table, the R table for 200 sample with alpha 0.05 is 0.1388. As the R value is bigger than R table, so all the question on the questionnaire is valid.

Table 1. Validity Result (Researcher's Analysis, 2023)

Variable	Question Item	Pearson Correlation Score	Description
Environment Concern	EC1	0.694	Valid
	EC2	0.723	Valid
	EC3	0.774	Valid
	EC4	0.792	Valid
	EC5	0.825	Valid
Green Perceived Benefit	GPB1	0.734	Valid
	GPB2	0.834	Valid
	GPB3	0.814	Valid
	GPB4	0.689	Valid
Willingness to Pay	WP1	0.827	Valid
	WP2	0.786	Valid
	WP3	0.840	Valid
Consumer Purchase Intention	CPI1	0.803	Valid
	CPI2	0.850	Valid
	CPI3	0.847	Valid
	CPI4	0.792	Valid

B. Reliability Test

According to Sürücü & Maslakçı (2020), Researchers attempting to determine reliability using the test-retest procedures approach to forecast reliability using the Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient or compare data using the t-test. The questionnaire is stated as reliable when the Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient is more than 0.6.

Table 2. Reliability Result (Researcher's Analysis, 2023)

Variable	Cronbach’s Alpha	Description
Environment Concern	0.815	Reliable
Green Perceived Benefit	0.768	Reliable
Willingness to Pay	0.752	Reliable
Consumer Purchase Intention	0.841	Reliable

The Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient on every variable is more than 0.6, which means that the questionnaire has internal consistency, so the questionnaire is reliable and consistent.

C. Regression Analysis

Regression analysis used to test the hypothesis of the researcher. The regression that used is the multiple linear regression analysis, this regression is used to determine the relationship between independent variable (Environment Concern (X1), Green Perceived Benefit (X2), and Willingness to Pay (X3)) on the dependent variable (Consumer Purchase Intention (Y)).

1) R Test

Table 3. R Test Result (Researcher's Analysis, 2023)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.737 ^a	0.543	0.536	1.726

Table 3. Above shown that the R value is 0.737, R value showing how strong the relationship between dependent variable with independent variable. R value is 0.737, which means the relationship between independent and dependent variable is strong. R square means that how much independent variable can have effect on dependent variable, so the variable independent (X1, X2, X3) can have effect on dependent variable (Y) about 54.3% and the other 45.7% have effect on variable Y with another variable beside variable independent.

2) Regression Coefficient

Table 4. Regression Coefficient (Researcher's Analysis, 2023)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.528	1.022		1.495	0.137
Environment Concern (X1)	0.337	0.057	0.363	5.929	0.000
Green Perceived Benefit (X2)	0.272	0.069	0.273	3.942	0.000
Willingness to Pay (X3)	0.288	0.070	0.247	4.101	0.000

The result of regression analysis on table 4. means that:

- The constant value for dependent variable (Consumer Purchase Intention (Y)) is 1.528.
- The regression coefficient Beta value of environment concern (X1) is 0.337, means that if variable X1 has increase the variable dependent Y (Consumer Purchase Intention) will increase by 0.337.
- The regression coefficient Beta value of green perceived benefit (X2) is 0.272, means that if variable X2 has increase the variable dependent Y (Consumer Purchase Intention) will increase by 0.272.

- The regression coefficient Beta value of willingness to pay (X3) is 0.288, means that if variable X3 has increase the variable dependent Y (Consumer Purchase Intention) will increase by 0.288.

3) Hypothesis Analysis (F Test)

Table 5. F Test Result (Researcher's Analysis, 2023)

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	694.149	3	231.383	77.67	0.000 ^b
Residual	583.846	196	2.979		
Total	1277.995	199			

Table 5. above shown the F value on regression analysis, which show as 77.67. The significant F is 0.000 which means it's smaller than 0.05 and the F table for this research is 2.65 with alpha 0.05, so F value is bigger than F table. The value mention means that the independent variable (X1, X2, X3) can have impact on dependent variable (Y). Overall, the result for regression test and the hypothesis is that consumer purchase intention (Y) is influence by environment concern (X1), green perceived benefit (X2), willingness to pay (X3) and the hypothesis is accepted.

CONCLUSION

Since sustainable fashion brand who applying slow and circular fashion concept to their product, the price of the product is high and only consumers who have high purchasing power can afford to buy the product. Many people who have high purchasing power didn't aware of the environment concern but the millennials and gen Z who have high awareness of environment concern have low purchasing power. This research wanted to find the factors that can influence the purchase intention of consumers on the slow and circular fashion concept. This research had identified the factors that influence consumers purchase intention on slow and circular fashion concept, which is the environment concern, green perceived benefit, and willingness to pay. The relationship between variable independent and dependent were positive, which means the variable independent can increase the variable dependent. This means the environment concern, green perceived benefit, and willingness to pay can increase purchase intention of the consumers.

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